
LEXICO-SEMANTIC PROCESSES IN THE FORMATION THE TERMINOLOGY IN THE SPHERE OF ALTERNATIVE MEDICINE

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Annotation.

Lexico-semantic word-formation processes of the formation of medical terminology and secondary nomination through borrowing and terminologization have been demonstrated in this article. Thorough analysis of this process and a great deal of dictionaries as well as literature related to this issue helped to determine that the lexico-semantic formation and secondary nomination as its variety proved to be productive ways of term formation.

Key words.

medical and paramedical terms, in the sphere of alternative medicine, formation of medical terminology, lexical unit of a particular language, classification of names, micro terminal systems, trans terminology.

Introduction.

Modern medical terminology is represented by a complex system, a set of medical and paramedical terms that have developed as a result of the centuries-old development of world medicine and medical science, which is still developing dynamically. There is a simultaneous process of combining disciplines that existed separately at the beginning of the XXI century in the medical field and division, differentiation of specialties into highly specialized ones. Second-generation disciplines appeared as independent areas of medicine: space biology and medicine, telemedicine, medical informatics, medical radiology, medical genetics, nanomedicine (including nanooncology, nanopharmacology, and nanostomatology), alternative medicine. The issues of the formation of the lexico-semantic system, the replenishment and study of its layers are among the significant areas of modern linguistics, which is facilitated by the need to form a systematized, unified terminological system in the medical field.

The purpose of this article is to demonstrate the lexico-semantic word-formation processes of the formation of medical terminology and secondary nomination through borrowing and terminologization.

Each term is based on a lexical unit of a particular language (V.M. Leichik [2] calls it a term substrate), which acquires specific features in the terminology. At the same time, the term is characterized by common lexical features, in particular, it retains the ability to exist in the totality of variants (just like an ordinary word). Terms are not special words, but words with a special function - to be a sign of a concept in a term system. Researchers recognize the fact that a term, like any other lexeme, has phonetic, derivational, morphological, word combination and other features of natural language units [9].

A medical term, according to the author's definition, is a language unit that preserves common lexical features of natural language units in a medical terminological database (macrosystem), which is a collection of collective knowledge of conventional and complementary (non-conventional) medicine (microsystems) . Complementary medicine in most countries is considered partly as folk, partly as modern traditional, but not having proper scientific confirmation, but not being an antagonist of science. Under the condition of an integrative medical approach, doctors combine the conventional, i.e. conventional, medical practice with methods and means of complementary and alternative medicine. Thus, modern medical terminology is a complex system of expression, storage and transmission of special medical and paramedical terms, which has a certain classification hierarchy, functioning over a long period and at the same time dynamic in terms of expression and content, allowing changes in the classification of names in connection with new discoveries in the field of study.

At the terminological level, the stratification of medical terminology is multilevel. S.V. Grinev-Grinevich presents a summary classification scheme of the concepts of the topic "Term formation", which is used by linguists- terminologists for the purposes of research and subsequent analysis of special terms in many areas according to the ways they appear [1]. Medical terminology can also be classified along this pattern, suggesting a division into:

- 1) semantic methods of term formation, including intersystem borrowing of lexemes and borrowing of foreign lexemes and term elements , terminology of the commonly used meaning of a word, metaphorization, metonymic transfer;
- 2) morphological methods of term formation;
- 3) syntactic way of term formation;

4) morphological and syntactic methods of term formation.

Microterminal systems that serve individual medical fields and represent highly specialized classifications of terms represent a single network of medical language. The microterminal system of the sublanguage of dentistry, being a part of general medical terminology, is both a complete complex system of terms, reflecting the system of concepts of an independent medical discipline, and an emerging narrowly focused specialized microsystem, due to a change in the surrounding picture of the world, technological progress and the emergence of modern approaches and methods of cognition. It is a dynamically developing discipline, which is a system of knowledge about diseases of the oral cavity and their treatment, methods of diagnostic research and disease prevention. At the same time, each dental specialization generates its own highly specialized vocabulary and forms its own terminological apparatus.

Semantic methods of term formation prevail in the process of terminological medical apparatus formation due to the borrowing of lexemes not only from language to language, but also from system to system (or from system to subsystem).

After conducting a randomized selection and subsequent study of terms, the author identified a large number of terms borrowed from language to language used in dentistry: luting (from the English - "putty") - fixing the restoration both with the help of cements and with the help of adhesive technique; microbrush (from English microbrush - "small brush") - an applicator designed for applying etching dental gels, bonding systems, fluid materials, etc.; polisher (from German Polieren - "polish, grind" < lat. Polio - "make smooth") - a tool for polishing dental fillings, having a spherical head, driven by a drill; grills (from English grills - "lattices") - a decorative grille or lining, an unusual decoration on one or more front teeth; pinlay tab (from English pinlay : pin "pin" + inlay - "make an insert) - microprosthesis , strengthened in the tooth with the help of pins (pins) located in the hard tissues of the tooth; scraper (from it . Schaber - "scraper") - a dental tool in the form of a small file with an extended working part, used for manual processing of removable dentures, etc.

The microterminal system of dental nanotechnologies clearly demonstrates the intersystem borrowing of units through the integration of knowledge and borrowing terms from many fields of science, such as: colloid chemistry, cell physiology, surface chemistry and biophysics, materials science, molecular biology, informatics, etc. [8.].

We demonstrate this statement with the following examples:

- 1) mineralogy: nano-hydroxyapatite (eng. nanohydroxy apatite), nanodiamond (English: nanodiamond);
- 2) pharmacy: nanocapsule (nanocapsule), nanoanesthesia (eng. nanoanaesthesia), nanodrugs (Eng. nanopharmaceuticals);
- 3) robotics and electronic devices, microelectromechanics : dental nanorobots (English dental nanorobots), laboratory-on-a-chip (Eng. Lab - on -a- chip), nanocomputer (Eng. nanocomputer);
- 4) chemistry: nanozone (Eng. nanozon), polymer (eng. polymer), etc.

Thus, as a result of the interaction of the two sciences, the terms of dentistry under the influence of nanoscience in both English and Russian acquire new meanings or shades of meaning, i.e. rethinking of the semantics of the word.

It should be noted that many terms borrowed from other sciences have undergone terminology , which is the main process that regulates the transition of a preterm into a term, i.e. the acquisition by a commonly used word of a new terminological meaning in a specific subject area, in a specific sublanguage [7]. So, for example, the word "mirror" in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language by S. I. Ozhegov has the following meanings: "1. An object with a polished glass or metal surface designed to display what is in front of it. 2. trans. Calm smooth surface of the waters. 3. Surface, area (of a river, reservoir, groundwater) (special)"[5]. In medicine, the common word "mirror" is terminologically acquiring a professional meaning: "The general name for a number of instruments designed to expand abdominal wounds and natural channels or to examine surfaces hidden from direct observation; they are straight or curved plates with polished surfaces or glass mirrors in an appropriate frame" [4]. In the field of dentistry, this term has undergone transterminologization , as a result of which a new highly professional meaning has been fixed: "dental mirror" - a small flat glass mirror, fixed at the end of a metal rod, intended for examining the teeth and oral cavity. Transterminologization , according to A.V. Superanskaya, this phenomenon of the transition of a term from one term system to another, in which the meaning changes, is one of the types of secondary terminological nomination [10].

Let's demonstrate one more example of transterminology. The term "probe" originally meant: "1. The name of various tools and devices for the study of soil, wells during drilling, the insides of the body. 2. Balloon with a special device for meteorological observations" [6]. In medicine, the term "probe" has acquired the

meaning of a medical instrument in the form of a rod, an elastic tube for insertion into hollow organs or wounds for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes; root needles. The medical encyclopedia contains about 30 terms with the meaning of the probe [3]. In the field of dentistry, this term is represented by the following variants:

1) dental probe - a multifunctional instrument used during each surgical procedure to determine the condition of the gums, periodontium, etc.;

periodontal probe - a tool used to identify and examine periodontal pockets.

Thus, terms that have undergone terminology often undergo significant transformations, leading to the fixation of highly specialized meanings.

Conclusion

Terminology as a set of vocabulary, which has the greatest informative load, is an open and heterogeneous system. In addition, the limits between the common word and the term are to a certain extent conditional, as well as between the term, professionalism and jargon. All this predetermines the continuous process of transition of units from one group to another with a complete or partial loss of value, the acquisition of a new value [7]. Analyzing the terms of medical encyclopedic dictionaries, publications, textbooks, the author comes to the conclusion that a huge information base of terms in the medical field is presented in combination with the terms of individual sciences and fields of knowledge. Therefore, they are useful from the point of view of the study of term systems and the replenishment of medical knowledge, since they are a source of generally accepted medical, emerging terms and terms of complementary medicine. They contain information about the etymology of terms, their definitions, where in the future they go through the process of ordering. The given examples show that lexico-semantic formation and secondary nomination as its variety remain productive ways of term formation.

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